

Tryptophan Participation in Melanogenesis : Modification of Raper-Mason-Pawelek Scheme of Melanin Formation¹

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In course of our studies on pigment metabolism in relation to vitiligo which primarily involves depletion of skin melanin, we concluded from the urinary indole profile² of vitiliginous patients that they have abnormal tryptophan metabolism. Subsequently, we showed³ that vitiliginous patients have higher blood tryptophan pyrrolase and tyrosine levels than normal subjects. We further showed that tryptophan pyrrolase and tyrosinase are in inverse relationship during experimental depigmentation or its regeneration with pigmentogenic drug psoralen⁴. The presence of abnormal tryptophan metabolism in vitiliginous patients were supported by investigations of Kurbanov and Berezov⁵, wherein it has been shown that vitiliginous patients, on higher tryptophan loading, elaborates more kyneurinine, 3-hydroxyanthranilic acid and 5-hydroxyindolylacetic acid through their urine. It also appears from our experiments that there is inhibition of the pigmentogenic enzyme tyrosinase and DOPA autooxidation due to higher tryptophan loading in mammalian system. It has further been shown by Chakraborty *et al.*⁶ that tryptophan can start melanisation in growing B₁₆-B₁₀ melanoma cells. All these experimental data led us to believe that melanogenesis in vitiligo is intimately connected with tryptophan metabolism. In fact Chen and Chavin⁷, as early in 1965, showed that tryptophan could be used as a substrate for gold fish tyrosinase for their melanin formation. Tryptophan has been shown to be incorporated into cuttle fish melanin nearly in 1/40 proportion as compared with the incorporation of tyrosine by Nicholas⁸. De Antonio *et al.*⁹ however showed that tryptophan via kyneurinine pathway could be incorporated into melanin of Harding-Passey mouse melanoma to the same extent as was incorporated when tyrosine was used as a substrate.

In a previous communication¹⁰, we showed that indole could be used as a substrate for melanin formation *in vitro* by biomimetic hydroxylation using Udenfriend reaction (Fe²⁺/EDTA/ascorbic acid/O₂). The obligatory indole skeleton required for bio-melanin formation through well-known tyrosine pathway could also arise from tryptophan with the loss of 3-carbon side chain. In consideration of the above reports and conjecture, we were interested to effect biomimetic synthesis of melanin from tryptophan using Udenfriend system (Fe²⁺/ascorbic acid/EDTA/O₂). For comparative studies, we also carried out experiments with tyrosine as the

substrate. The results of this model reaction might provide us with information regarding various probable chemical species which might participate in the regulation of melanin synthesis as it has been shown by Pawelek *et al.*¹¹ that biosynthesis of melanin from tyrosine in Cloudman melanoma cells involves complex regulatory factors. Our results may help in the understanding of melanogenic process with special reference to vitiligo. Here we report our results and suggest a modification of Raper-Mason-Pawelek scheme of tyrosine melanin synthesis with the participation of tryptophan and also the catabolism of the amino acid substrates in relation to depletion of melanin in vitiligo.

Experimental

All experiments were carried out at room temperature (30–32°). Tyrosine (Merck), tryptophan (Merck), ascorbic acid (Sarabhai Chemicals) and other chemicals used in the experiments were all of A.R. grade.

The solutions of substrates (L-tryptophan, 306 mg in 30 ml water; L-tyrosine, 271 mg in 30 ml water) were added in separate experiments to a mixture of reagents consisting of 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.7; 250 ml), ascorbic acid (616 mg) and EDTA (604.5 mg). The reaction mixture was stirred and a solution of FeSO₄·7H₂O (90.5 mg) was added dropwise over a period of 15 min. The stirring was continued for 240 min with tryptophan, and 120 min with tyrosine in two different experiments respectively, in an atmosphere of oxygen. On allowing the reaction mixture to stand, deposits of black particles which were collected by centrifuging (800 rpm, 10 min) and the properties compared with DOPA melanin (Sigma). The aqueous solution was then extracted with solvent ether. On evaporation of the solvent a brown mass was obtained. The constituents in the brown mass were separated on a tic plate (silica gel, 20 × 10 cm; solvent system: benzene–acetone, 9:1). The spots were detected by various spray reagents and were cut out and the compounds were collected by extraction with ethyl acetate. The homogeneous compounds so obtained were characterised by their uv, ir and mass spectral data (all the compounds) as well as in some cases by direct comparison with authentic specimens (5, 6, 7, 8). The properties of compounds 1–10 are detailed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF COMPOUNDS (1–10) ISOLATED FROM BIOMIMETIC REACTIONS OF TYROSINE/TRYPHTOPHAN UNDER UDENFRIEND CONDITIONS

Compd. no.	M p. °C	Mass M ⁺	R _t (C ₆ H ₆ - Acetone, 1 : 1)	Colour reaction*	λ _{max} (EtOH) nm (log ε)	ν _{max} cm ⁻¹
1	220	180	0.11	Orange red ^b	—	8 450, 1 700, 1 600
2	274–75	186	0.21	Orange red ^b	—	8 500, 1 620
3	154	149	0.24	Blue ^c	222(8.8), 276(8.8), 298(8.75)	Material insufficient
4	—	165	0.25	Violet ^c	—	8 450, 8 400, 1 600
5 ^a	52	117	0.98	Reddish pink ^c	—	—
6 ^a	146	137	0.11	Yellow ^c	245(3.56), 322(3.2)	8 500, 8 400, 1 680, 1 620
7 ^a	240	143	0.035	Yellow ^c	320(3.5), 252(3.52)	8 400, 1 655, 1 610, 1 580
8 ^a	202.5	147	0.20	Orange ^c	240(5.6), 292(4.0)	8 200, 1 740, 1 760, 1 630
9	169	171	0.15	Faint pink ^c	252(2.9)	8 400, 1 685, 1 170, 1 885
10	110–14	203	0.16	Orange ^b Gray violet ^c	—	8 400, 1 740, 1 700, 1 610, 1 590

*Identified by comparison with authentic specimen.
^aWith ^bDNP reagent, ^cEhrlich reagent.

Results

The results of the above reaction show that under Udenfriend conditions tryptophan and tyrosine, like indole, furnished melanin, having properties like DOPA melanin. The melanin in both the cases were soluble in alkali and was decolourised by alkaline hydrogen peroxide. The uv spectral data of melanin and the ir data (3 400, 1 640, 1 620 cm⁻¹) compared well with the DOPA melanin (3 400, 1 720, 1 640, 1 620 cm⁻¹).

From tyrosine, besides melanin, *p*-hydroxyphenylpyruvic acid (1), 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl (2), 5,6-dihydroxyindole (3) and 5,6,3-trihydroxyindole (4) were obtained. From tryptophan, besides melanin, indole (5) anthranilic acid (6), 3-hydroxyanthranilic acid (7), isatin (8), 3-hydroxypyrrole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid (9) and 5,6-dihydroxyindole (3) and indolylpyruvic acid (10) were obtained.

- 1; R₁ = OH, COOOH, R₂ = R₃ = H, R₄ = OH
 6; R₁ = COOH, R₂ = NH₂, R₃ = R₄ = H
 7; R₁ = COOH, R₂ = NH₂, R₃ = OH, R₄ = H

- 3; R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = OH
 4; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = OH
 5; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H
 10; R₁ = CH₂CO.OOOH, R₂ = R₃ = H

Discussion

Our results in this model monooxygenase reaction show that *in vitro* formation of melanin and 5,6-dihydroxyindole is accompanied by other products resulting from the oxidation of indole skeleton. Our results on hydroxylation of tryptophan appear to be consistent with results reported by Viscontini¹⁰ who used modified Udenfriend system and obtained 5-hydroxytryptophan, indole-3-acetic acid, skatol, kynurenine and its degradation products along with melanin. Pawelek *et al.*¹¹ has recently shown that biosynthesis of melanin in Cloudman melanoma cells is a complex process and is regulated by three factors: (i) dopa chrome conversion factor which converts dopa chrome to 5,6-dihydroxyindole (3), (ii) 5,6-dihydroxyindole conversion factor which catalyses the conversion of 5,6-dihydroxyindole to melanin and is active when cells are exposed to melanotropin (MSH) and (iii) 5,6-dihydroxyindole blocking factor which restricts melanogenesis at 5,6-dihydroxyindole stage. They have further shown that at least three steps in Raper-Mason hypothesis of melanin formation from tyrosine are catalysed by tyrosinase.

The oxidation products 6, 7 and 9 arising from tryptophan could arise through a reaction resembling *in vivo* dioxygenase reaction on the intermediate products leading to 3 and melanin. Compounds 4 and 9 could be considered to be candidates which might participate in detoxication mechanism of 5,6-dihydroxyindole as indole itself is detoxicated

Scheme 1. Combined tyrosine and tryptophan participation for the synthesis of melanin and catabolism in relation to melanin synthesis in vitiligo (modification of Raper-Mason-Pawelek scheme).

through its 3-hydroxy derivative. Similar function of the 5,6-dihydroxyindole blocking factor has been envisaged by Pawelek. Such a chemical transformation of 5,6-dihydroxyindole might relieve the cell from the cytotoxic effect of 3. The overall results of the model reactions suggest that substrates of melanin may undergo transformations through

reactions, simulating monooxygenase and dioxigenase reaction *in vivo*. Probably the production of end-products is regulated by the metabolism-dependent kinetics of these type of reactions.

The concomitant deamination of amino acid substrates, tyrosine and tryptophan have been

observed in our experiments. In case of tyrosine a well-known inhibitors of tyrosine, *p*-hydroxyphenylpyruvic acid (1) has been isolated which undergoes further transformation after the cleavage of the side chain. Due to deamination, tyrosine is withdrawn as a substrate for melanin formation while tryptophan may give rise to 5,6-dihydroxyindole (3) through 10 and 5. Tryptophan *in vivo* may play a role in counteracting the effect of withdrawal of the substrate tyrosine through deamination. Deamination may aid amelanoses in vitiligo due to the formation of 1 and the recovery of melanin from tryptophan in vitiliginous patients may be more difficult than normal subjects due to higher level of tryptophan pyrrolase⁴.

Our results show that *in vitro* melanin formation is a complex process requiring the regulation of various participating reactions, i.e. monooxygenases/dioxygenases/deamination. The results may have relevance to Pawelek's regulating factors *in vivo* melanin formation. In short, hitherto not well-established tryptophan participation, has gained further ground due to the work of Chakraborty and Chakraborty (unpublished data) wherein it has been shown that tryptophan under different condition like DOPA can augment and also inhibit melanin formation. It can also act as a substrate for it. From the present biomimetic experiments and reports in literature, it is evident that 5,6-dihydroxyindole, the precursor of melanin, may arise from both tyrosine and tryptophan due to the action of monooxygenases *in vivo* or their prototypes *in vitro*.

This could be represented in a modified Raper-Mason-Pawelek^{1*} scheme of melanin synthesis as depicted in Scheme 1. On the other hand, the catabolism of the amino acids or the intermediate precursors of melanin may be due to participation of dioxygenase or other participating reactions. The catabolic aspects of these chemical species may provide the regulatory factor for normal production of 5,6-dihydroxyindole excess of which would otherwise be toxic to normal cells. In this dynamics of melanin formation, both monooxygenase and dioxygenase species of enzyme participate and probably the extent of limitation of the reactivity of these two types of enzyme together with other metabolic factors regulate the normal status of melanin in biological system. In vitiligo the impairment of melanogenesis may take place due to higher catabolic activities. The catabolism of amino acids and

of the chemical species considered to be precursors of melanin could be withdrawn from the system by reactions including dioxygenases or deamination. This has also been shown in Scheme 1. The activities of dioxygenases like indoleamine-2,3-dioxygenase¹⁴ (Chakraborty *et al.*, unpublished data), tryptophan pyrrolase⁸ which have higher level in vitiliginous patients, are super-oxide anion dependent. In considerations of the data, discussion presented and different aspects of molecular mechanism of oxygen activation¹⁵, it may be a relevant conjecture that vitiligo may also be associated with oxygen fixation or oxygen toxicity in the body.

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